

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The Russo-Turkish War in Crimea and Nightingale's Role in It (1854-1855)

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(02), 395–397

Publication history: Received on 29 March 2023; revised on 07 May 2023; accepted on 09 May 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.2.0746>

Abstract

In October 1853, the Ottoman Empire declared war on Russia, after a series of disputes over the holy places in Jerusalem and Russian claims to protect the Orthodox subjects of the Ottoman Empire. The British and French, allies of the Ottoman Empire, sought to check Russian expansion. The majority of the Crimean War took place in Crimea, Russia. However, the British troop base and hospitals for the care of sick and wounded soldiers were established primarily at Scutari (Uskudar), across the Bosphorus from Constantinople (Istanbul). As the war broke out, reports returned to Britain about the terrible conditions for the sick and wounded British soldiers. Popular on the mistreatment of wounded British soldiers, a friend of Florence Nightingale, the Secretary of War, Sidney Herbert, wrote to Florence and asked her to lead a group of nurses to attend the headquarters of the British forces. So Florence Nightingale volunteered to go to Turkey then known as Scutari, accompanied by thirty-eight women, including eighteen Catholic, Anglican and Roman sisters, to war.

Keywords: Russo-Turkish War; Crimea; Nightingale's Role

1. Introduction

The Angel's Band, as some rightly call it, set out quietly under the cover of darkness on the evening of the twenty-first of October, 1854, accompanied by a priest, a courier, and some of Nightingale's friends. Nightingale's decision to agree to volunteer was announced in *The Times* on October 23 of the same year. It took Florence and her fellow nurses thirteen days to reach Scutari. They traveled by ship to Boulogne, then overland to Marseille, where they stopped on the journey. From Marseille they took the mail steamer *Vestez* to Scutari [1].

Florence Nightingale arrived in Scutari with the nurses on the 4th of November 1854. Conditions in the hospitals were very poor and hundreds of soldiers had been wounded in the fighting. The hospitals were very primitive, and the soldiers were not receiving good food and medicine to help them get better. Florence saw that the wounded slept in crowded, filthy rooms without any blankets. Soldiers often arrived with diseases such as typhoid fever and cholera, but more men died from these diseases than from their injuries. When Florence arrived at the hospital, the army doctors who worked there did not want to help the nurses. But soon after their arrival, a very big battle took place, the Battle of Inkerman, and the doctors realized that they needed that help from the nurses. For her part, Florence knew that if doctors were going to let her nurses work, they had to do a very good job. Of the thirty-eight nurses who went out with Miss Nightingale, twenty-four were trained from the Sisters, Roman and Anglican, and of the remaining fourteen, some from Florence were chosen to be in the first place of those nurses, especially of critical and emergency cases [2].

Florence mentioned in her memoirs how she found a forbidden barracks in the Scutari Hospital, which housed ten thousand sick men, with dirt and filth all over the hospital, the patients lying in the corridors as well as in the wards. When it rained the water ran through the roof, the food was inedible, and the water allowance was only one pint a day; The buildings were infested with vermin; The atmosphere in the hospital is stinky, as soon as she visits the wards she

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makes Florence and her fellow nurses sick. So clean up the hospital, wash the sheets, blankets, and towels, clean up the hospital kitchens, and prepare better food for the patients [3]. Most important of all, Florence hired military engineers to repair the hospital's sewers and improve the drinking water supply. By the spring of 1855 Florence was physically exhausted from the strenuous working conditions in the Crimea, but as a result of her efforts, the death rate in Scutari was greatly reduced [4]. Teachers are the main caregivers and the first line of protection for school children. Their role complements that of parents. During school hours, school teachers are actually the first-respondent in cases of disasters or emergencies. They must be able to deal properly with health emergencies both in normal children, and those children with special health care needs [5].

2. Methodology

Florence Nightingale headed the nursing effort in the British military hospitals in Scutari for the period (1854-1856), and she laid down sanitary conditions and ordered supplies, starting with clothes and bedding. It gradually outmaneuvered the military doctors, or at least enough to win their co-operation. She soon concentrated more on the health administration than on actual nursing, but continued to visit the wards and send messages home for the wounded and sick. Her rule was to be the only woman walking between the wards during the night. With her presence and tireless work, the death rate at the military hospital dropped from sixty percent when it was reached to a mere two percent six months later. Florence applied her education and interest in mathematics to the development of statistical analysis of morbidity and mortality, and to inventing the use of the pie chart. She fought military bureaucracy and, while there, contracted a fever, but nonetheless rose to become general superintendent of the Women's Nursing Establishment in the Army's military hospitals on March 16, 1856.

3. Results and discussion

Based on these developments, Barrack the director of the Scutari Hospital gave a letter on the 14th of November 1854 in her letter stating that we had 1175 sick and wounded in this hospital (of which 120 were patients with cholera), and (650) seriously wounded in the other building, called the General Hospital of which we are in charge Also, when I reached Florence, where the battle was going on, the number of casualties increased (1,763) wounded and (442) dead, as well as 96 officers wounded (38) I expected to end my days as head of the hospital, and I never expected to be a barrack lady. We had but half an hour before they began to get the wounded in. Between one and nine o'clock in the morning the mattresses were stuffed and stitched, they lay (unfortunately only on a mat on the floor), the men were washed and put to bed, all their wounds covered." Angel...Yet, in the midst of this awful terror (we are up to our necks in blood) there is good--and I can truly say, like St. Peter it is good that we are..."

At the end of the Crimean War, and as a result of Florence Florence Nightingale's determination and insistence on her work in Scutari Hospital, and then for her role in developing nursing as a profession, she was dubbed "The Lady with the Lamp", because she used to go out in the darkness of the night to the battlefields, carrying a lamp in her hand, to search for the wounded And the injured were to be treated, and the treatment this woman received at the hands of the military was not in a better condition than what the war correspondents received from them. It was published under this title in The Times of the 8th of February, 1855, which says: "She is without any exaggeration a 'deceitful angel' of these hospitals, and while her slender figure glides quietly along every aisle, every poor fellow's face softens with gratitude at the sight of her." All the medical officers retired for the night, and silence and darkness settled these miles from a prostrate patient, who could be seen alone, with a little lamp in her hand, making her solitary rounds." The mention of patients' miles relates to contemporary reports that the wards at Scutari extended for four miles..

4. Conclusion

All thanks to those who helped me complete and publish the research And benefit society through the culture of peoples

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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